

Case Study Measurement of the Sustainability Performance of Indian Pulses Firms via Performance Measurement and Management System and Balanced Scorecard Method

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Abstract:

The sustainable performance of production and operation processes of all pulse processing firms to generate efficient pulse processing processes. The case study adopted the balanced scorecard method (SCORE) and performance measurement and management system (P.M.M.S.) technique, which has performed on sustainability indicators on different production and operation parts of selected pulses firms. The pulse firms are selected from the following states are Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan, and Delhi /NCR regions. The analysis of sustainability factors determines the current status of pulse processing firms and describes each risk factors that affect the performance of pulse processing firms. The study considers all

internal and external factors of the manufacturing process with a sustainability dimension are applies with quantitative analysis techniques to achieve the production and operation at optimum levels. The case study describes the performance measurement and management systems techniques and balances scorecard method, which generates Information to develop strategic decision-making, and also develops the key performance indicators to analyze the firms' financial and nonfinancial measures. The case study developed the conceptual model framework structure of PMMS and balanced scorecard method, that firms are implementing the score techniques at different levels and explains their process in an organization, also measuring the sustainability performance of firms. The case study analyses the various significant levels of risk, which made the direct impact on the sustainability performance of all selected pulse firms and define the current status of pulse firms also discussed the implementation of pulse value chain practices. The case study generates the relevant Information which is applied for decision-making, also reduces the major constraint of all pulse's firms.

Keywords: *Sustainability, perspectives, significance, production, operation.*

Introduction

India is the largest pulse-producing country in the world, that contributes about 25% of global

pulse production. Pulses production has covered 20 % of the area under the food grains. Indian pulse processing firms are highly dependent upon pulse production that produce quality

pulse seeds. The case study adopted the performance measurement and management systems for measuring the sustainability performance of selected pulses firms, therefore the case study covered the selected zones of India are Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan, and Delhi states. The pulses processing industries. are facing major challenges such as lack of technology, machine breakage, high adoption of old techniques, and lack of quality seeds, which affect the performance of the manufacturing process and cause less processed food production and developed variations in demographic factors which causes the decline of pulses firms. Therefore, selected pulse firms are required to adopted various methodologies and innovative technologies to remove those constraint and generate quality processed foods with different brands that support the future pulse market. The assessment tool applied in pulse firms, are performed with different techniques to enhanced the production efficiency, maintain the balance between supply and demand of processed pulses food and reached optimum level of production, also improved the consumer choices and promoted the acceptance of pulses processed food. It is essential that all pulse firms developed the awareness and achieve long-term goals and objectives. The pulses processing company adopted the pulses value chain practices, which increased the value addition of processed food and enhanced the supply chain process. With the support of balanced score card techniques, all selected pulse firms achieve the maximum gain as forms of financial profit and produce a wide variety of processed pulse food that meets the current and future market requirements. Moreover, the balanced score card techniques reduces the challenges of pulse production, and forced the adoption of different sustainability measures and pulse value chain practices to increase the quality of pulse production, achieve long-term benefits in the forms of high-quality pulse production, also generate sustainability aspects. The selected pulses firms are applied the another techniques are performance measurement and management system techniques to upgrade the operational systems and generate efficient resource

management practices to achieve high financial gains. The performance measurement and management system method identifies pulse firms and shows the current status with the sustainability measure strategic factors. The PMMS performance measurement and management system method is based on quantitative techniques to analyze all internal and external factors, with sustainability measures, that directly impact on performance of pulse firms and generate the expected output. (Neely et al., 1995). It also implies the systematic assignment of several key performance indicators and their entities. (Shahin. A., 2012). The performance measurement and management system techniques are applied in the food industry, that focusing on analysing the environmental, social, and economic aspects and enhancing the supply chain management with sustainability dimensions. The PMMS performance measurement and management system identifies the usage of raw materials, generates production planning, and measures the environmental impact on pulse production, that reduces the risk of operational manufacturing failure. (Guillermo et.al., 2021). Similarly, the case study adopted the balanced scorecard method to develop the design and feasibility for applying sustainability measures in pulse production and enhanced the operational part of pulse firms. The balanced scorecard is applied as an analytical hierarchy process to perform the comprehensive performance evaluation of pulse processing firms and is widely implemented in the supply chain, improve the organization's responsibility mechanisms, and improve employee awareness participation processes to generate enhanced output. (Song, 2022). The balanced card methods are highly recommended for continuous development and generate advantages through better communication and developed integration with the different functional areas. Moreover, it generates the key performance indicator to measure the sustainability performance of pulse firms. The balanced scorecard (score) technique achieved those objectives and generated the need to transform business strategies effectively throughout the organization channel and also

played the critical role of efficiently integrating the operational procedure and improving the evaluation process. (Kopecka, 2015). The research study is classified into different objectives. The first objective consists of a literature review based on the study of different performance assessment techniques, the study describes the performance measurement and management system PMMS and their framework structure adopted by pulses processing firms in their operation system to achieve long-term goals and objectives. The second objective defined the balanced scorecard method and developed the conceptual frame structure model of the balanced scorecard method to measure sustainability performance and show how pulse firms implement score techniques in pulses firms. The third objectives the case study describes the significant level of risk which made direct impacts of sustainability performance of all selected 25 pulse firms, also considers the internal and external factors of pulse firms. These practices help firms to develop strategic decisions and reduce the constraints of all pulse processing firms, which are facing critical situations during the adoption of pulse value chain practices. (Liebe truth et. al., 2017).

Research Objectives

1. To analyze the performance measurement and management system PMMS method with balanced scorecard method score techniques are applied in pulse firms.
2. To analyze the different levels of significance of all risk factors that made a direct impact on pulses firms' performance by using performance measurement and management system.

Literature Review

The literature review discussed the scope of sustainability measurement techniques, and their impact on the external and internal factors, of all manufacturing firms. The sustainability approach is applied to develop the integration with performance measurement and management systems (PMMS) for improving the

firm performance and generates effectiveness. (Liebe truth. et. al., 2017, and provides the advantages of technology adoption and conducts performance measurement, which promotes digitalization. (Kumar et. al., 2018), Supply chain management in the food processing industry is increasingly applying multiple methodologies and approaches to assessing the firms' performance. (Guillermo et. al., 2021), and enhanced the current performance evaluation system of enterprises and developed the feasibility techniques of designing performance evaluation through PMMS techniques. (Song, 2022). The balanced scorecard approach is applied for the continuous development of firms to determine the advantages and disadvantages of firms' practices and develop the key performance indicators. (Kopecka, 2015). A balanced scorecard developed the integration of operational procedure with the key performance indicator to measure the strategy for the best formulation of translated strategies. (Kopecka.(2015). The balanced scored card method is based upon sustainability measurement techniques, which become sufficient management tools and procedures (Ahan. h, 2001). And also provides accurate, timely information and develops communication among manufacturing firms. Balanced scorecards are considered the effective performance evaluation method, for developing the competitive strategies of firms to achieve long-term goals, and comparing the financial measures of small and medium-sized firms. (João et.al., 2013). The performance assessment techniques analyze the economic crises to develop an integrated view of the performance of firms and develop the structure equation model related to strategic planning (Waluyo et. al., 2016), the operational assessment of firms played a vital role for strategy formulation and the develop the key operational factors to identify the goals and product quality. (Jalaiyam et al. (2014), also combined the one- and two-step models, with the support of seven semantics points and made an assessment to develop the structure equation model. (Chrisovanlantis et. al., 2020). The Balanced Scorecard (B.S.C.) method becomes a powerful and effective tool that can provide an integrated

view of an organization's performance measurement process. (Waluyo. et. al, 2014).

Performance Measurement and Management System

Performance measurement and management systems (SCPMS) are considered as sustainability measurement techniques applied in supply chain management and other manufacturing parts. The PMMS develops the feasibility and applicability of system design. The performance measurement and management system are applied in manufacturing firms and academic parts of the system. The performance measurement and management system has been applied to achieve the long-term goal, and measure system to design the feasibility and applicability of PMMS in the system. The performance measurement and management system generate the multi-dimension strategy, which identifies the company's requirements and improves the firm's need to provide service to diverse channels. Performance measurement are based on quantitative techniques has been applied to measure each segment and track the performance of products and services. The performance measures and management system are classified as nonfinancial measures and financial measures. The nonfinancial quantitative measures including the cycle time, customer service, inventory level, resource utilization, etc, are applied to measure the performance of firms and achieve the optimum level of each functional area. The financial measures consist of the fixed and operating costs related to the supply chain are considered the financial measures. The key objectives are to maximize the revenue through maintaining supply chain cost, the performance measurement and management system process is considered for inventory management, transportation facilities, operation technology, material, and labor. The financial performance of the supply chain is assessed through the following factors cost of raw material, revenue generated from goods sold activity cost, inventory holding cost, transportation cost, and cost of expired perished goods, etc. The financial performance index is applied as a key performance indicator based upon activity-based

costing, inventory costing, firms' economic costing, etc. (Neely et al., 1995) into various measure factors such as cost, time, quality, and flexibility, etc. are used for analyzing the working performance of business firms, with suitable techniques. (Chan et. al., 2003), Most firms applied the supply chain performance measurement system to identify the critical issues in the supply chain and manufacturing unit. The supply chain performance system (Shepherd et al., 2006) are applied in pulses processing firms to identify the internal and external factors and the key performance indicators, to set those metrics according to sustainability performance measurement and management system, (Gunasekaran et. al.2005). The study defines the PMMS in the figure, describes the critical part of firms, and performs the measurement procedure in manufacturing firms. The performance measurement and management system are classified into various categories in the Lifecycle phases, including the design approach and development of various functional units and performed continuous improvement process. The scope of PMMS is focused on the different available units, including internal and external factors, and generating a competitive environment, according to the usage of sustainability performance measurement and management system is required in business firms to develop the dynamic nature, generate a potential capacity of production and operational parts, and improve the supply chain process of firms. (Reddy. A, et. al., 2019).

The figure defines the performance measurement and management system as classified into different components such as conflict and objectives, technology challenges, attitude and commitment, and alignment. Each component consists of different key performance indicators, consisting of several factors that are directly linked to the supply chain performance measurement system, such as conflict and objective also linked with supply chain performance measurement systems. Several other components are technology challenges, including the ability to account for are directly linked with the supply chain

performance management system. Similarly, the other key performance indicators are attitude and commitment alignment, etc., which are mentioned in the figure to define their different

role and functions towards firms' performance measurement and management system and make direct links with the supply chain performance measurement system.

Figure 1. The Concept of Manufacturing Firms' Performance Measurement and Management System

Source: The evolution of performance measurement systems in a supply chain: A longitudinal case study on the role of inter-organizational factors (Kim et al. et al. 2018)

Balanced Score Method (SCOR)

The balanced scorecard method was developed by Kaplan and Norton in the year 1992. (Robert. et al., 1992) and applied to top-level manufacturing firms. The balanced scorecard method formulated the strategic objectives and identified the competitive environment of the business firms. The balanced scorecard method consists of four financial dimensions customer, internal process, learning, and growth perspectives in business firms, and allows to adopt the new performance measurement techniques that increase the employee potential capacity, generate the usage of information technology, and establish communications

among employees. Similarly, the other dimension of the balanced scorecard method is customer perspectives, which help to create value for customers. That is how firms generate customer values and perform the internal process perspectives that combine the production and operational functions and increase the efficiency of their functional area. The last dimension of a balanced score is the financial perspective, in which selected pulse firms achieve financial gain from pulse processing, develop cross-functional relationships in business firms, and improve problem-solving and decision-making. (Robert.S. et. al.,1992). The balanced scorecard method formulates a successful strategy and

develops the strategy-focused objectives (S.F.O.). (Robert. S et.al, 2000). In a balanced scorecard, the strategy-focused organization established the linkage between strategy implementation and established communication in the firms. Thus, the employees and employers drive the balanced scorecard method to carry out the business firms in their designing and implementation practices and develop a competitive environment for employers and other key stakeholders. (Specbacher et al., 2003). The balanced scorecard method achieves the following objectives to develop sustainability measurement tools in selected pulse processing firms. (Neely et al., 2000). The balanced scorecard method generates awareness of strategic objectives in established pulse firms. (Rompho, 2011). Moreover, they explained the key benefits of the balanced scorecard method in an organization with successful implantation of learning and growth perspectives. The balanced scorecard method generates various advantages as strategy formulation and develops the core competencies in manufacturing firms. The performed evaluation of a balanced scorecard is mainly divided into four dimensions: financial, customer, internal process, and learning and growth to provide long-term benefit to the key stakeholders, customers, employers, and employees of the firms. The sustainability performance tool focuses on each dimension of the balanced scorecard method to establish the link among employees and develop the causal relation of understanding the business performance. Therefore, the selected pulse firms of India should implement the balanced scorecard method to construct the performance evaluation index system. Firstly, it enhanced the sustainability measurement tool and developed the current performance measurement, which is based upon the financial key indicator that made a direct impact on the growth of business firm performance. The balanced scorecard method identifies the lack of current performance evaluation systems, generates the requirement for a suitable design approach for measuring the sustainability factors, and evaluates selected pulses processing firms in India (Song, 2022). The sustainability performance evaluation

system has achieved the goal and objectives of pulses firms are critical performance indicator assessment and developed the economic value added to provide the sustainability measurement tool and techniques in pulses firms. The Supply Chain Council created the balanced scorecard model, which developed the framework structure for examining supply chain practices and categorizing the processes into different segments that made an effective supply chain management system, assigning metrics to the processes, and developing the standard benchmarks. Many business firms have applied the SCOR model to understand and improve their supply chain practices. The balanced scorecard method (SCOR) contains thirteen metrics according to different levels in selected pulse firms.

The Given Figure Describes the Hierarchy Structure of the Balanced Scorecard Method

The top Level 1, categorizes the supply chain into various generate reliability, flexibility, responsiveness, cost, and assets metrics. Level 1, level 2, and Level 3 describe the process types, process categories, and process elements. The first three levels define the different functions of the organization and are applied in the operation of firms (Wong et al., 2008), The balanced scorecard method is implemented in selected pulse processing firms to measure the input and output variables and evaluate the supply chain system. (Thakkar et al., 2009). The balanced scorecard model supports the Performance Measurement System for establishing the pulse processing firms, to increase the manufacturing process's efficiency. (Reddy et al.,2019)

Each level in firms and identifies the problem of firms. The balanced SCOR card consists of two parts, which are applied as performance attributes and metrics. These metrics are considered the key performance indicators reliability, responsiveness, agility, cost, and assets management. The balanced scorecard techniques are embodied with qualitative and quantitative techniques to generate the relevant information for the quantities assessment process. (Jhon. 2014). The SCOR model has been applied in various firms to measure a

company's supply chain performance level, which could be used for future business improvement. The figure describes the balanced scorecard method, which consists of four main factors learning and growth, business processes, customers, and finance, which are applied in different level and functional areas to examine the business segment. The balanced scorecard combined the production and operation

functional area and enhanced the sustainability measure factors of selected pulses firms that developed the industrial policy. Moreover, the scoring method innovates new performance measurement techniques. The balanced scorecard technique promotes firms' strategic objectives at the top level and generates relevance of sustainability measurement tools.

Level	Level	Examples	Comments
1.	Process Type (Scope)	Plan, Source, Make, Deliver, Return and Enable	Level-1 defines scope and content of a supply chain. At level-1 the basis -of competition performance target for a supply chain are set.
2.	Process Categories Configuration	Make to stock, make to order, Engineer to design, Defective order, MRO product, Excess product	Level -2 define the operational strategies. At level -2 the process categories for a supply chain set (make to order, Make to stock)
3.	Process Element steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schedule delivery • Receive product • Verify product • Transfer product • Authorize Product 	Level-3 define the configuration of individual process. At level-3 the ability to execute is set. At level -3 the focus is on the right. Process Input and out put Process performance Practices Technologies capabilities Skill of staff
4.	Activities (implantation)	Industry company, location and /or technology specific steps	Level-4 describes the activities performed in the supply chain companies implement industry, and location specific process and practices to achieve required performance.

Figure 2. The Framework Structure of the Balanced Scorecard Method and Its Functional Area

Impact of Performance Measurement and Management System on Pulses Value Chain

The performance measurement and management system utilizes sustainability in the pulse value chain for performed to evaluate the key strategies and apply the best practices for driving sustainability in the pulse value chain and generate optimize operations, enhancing traceability, and promoting environment sustainability that helps to explore sustainability and develop resistance pulse value chain. performance measurement and management system developed mapping with pulses value chain and applied to flow of product from producer to ultimate consumer. The

performance measurement and management system in the pulse value chain are performed the various functions are developed to interlink several components a. With value chain actors (farmers) dealers, distributors b. Developed enabling environment with infrastructure and policies institute c. Service provider to support the value chain operation (Kumari et.al. 2018) effectively and give the expected out comes in the forms of pulses production.

Role of Performance Measurement and Management System in sustainability measures

Performance measurement and management systems manage the supply chain to develop coordination between different actors such as suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, and retailers to develop effective management of the supply chain and provide the numerous benefits that include.

a. **Cost Reduction:** performance measurement and management systems reduce costs to achieve the level of optimization and provide less reduction of transport costs and improved supplier performance. PMMS performance measurement and management system help to control and monitor the performance of firms through cost reduction and take immediate action for cost saving.

b. **Increased Efficiency** The performance measurement and management system could improve the speed and generate efficiency in supply chain management that reduces the lead time and improves customer satisfaction provide, through monitoring performance, generating efficiencies in your supply chain, and developing the proper steps for improving the processes and eliminating wastage.

c. **Improved Risk Management:** performance measurement and management systems played a significant role in business operations and identifying the potential risks and mitigating those risks, of different alternative suppliers.

d. **Better Decision Making:** the performance measurement and management system in supply chain management generates the relevant information that is applied for decision-making to maintain inventory management, and also generate production schedules to support the other aspects of the business.

e. **Competitive Advantage** A performance measurement and management system support supply chain management and generates competitive advantages by providing efficiency, reducing cost, and improving customer satisfaction which differentiate the

business from competitors and achieve the financial gain of a competitive edge.

f. **Key Performance Indicators:** performance measurement and management systems generate relevancy in business and achieve those targets for each transaction. The key performance indicators for supply chain management include inventory turnover, on-time delivery, order generation, lead time, and made different costs of goods sold, and supplier performance.

g. **Work with Suppliers:** suppliers play a vital role in maintaining the supply chain performance and develop regular meetings to discuss performance metrics and identify the areas for improvement.

h. **Continuous Improvement:** Supply chain performance is a continuous process that collects data, to analyze and identify the areas for improvement. The performance measurement and management system analyzes the performance of supply chain management which is essential to achieve success in today's competitive marketplace, and made a collection of data and, working with suppliers and made continuous improvements to achieve the optimization of the supply chain to generate the maximum efficiency and made effectiveness. This will improve customer satisfaction provide a competitive advantage and take a proactive approach to supply chain management.

Methodology

The research method adopted the performance measurement and management system (PMMS) with a balanced scorecard method to analyze the sustainability performance of the production and operation part of all pulses firms. The performance measurement and management system is a conceptual technique based on cost factors, time measures, quality measures, and flexibility measures and these factors are applied to measure the sustainability performance of firms, the other method is the balanced scorecard (scor) method adopted that consist of multi-dimension performance evaluation system. (Kaplan, 1992). Its primary purpose is to generate information applied in strategic

decision-making and increase the performance of business functional areas.

Result and Discussion

The data was collected from (25) sizes pulses firms in Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan, and India's Delhi / N.C.R. regions. The research study adopted the performance measurement and management system to measure the sustainability performance of all firms and applied the sustainability dimension for internal and external parts of pulses firms. The given tables generate the information that is applied to develop the strategic Information, improve the

mechanism of operation, also achieve the long-term goal of all firms.

The table is formed according to the firm's organizational structure and required sustainability measures. practices.

Cost Performance (Efficiency)

The table shows that 07 firms out of 25 firms have a deficient % of distribution cost, eight out of 25 firms have a low % of reduction of distribution costs, and 10 firms have a medium % reduction of distribution cost of transportation. Therefore large number of pulse firms have medium distribution costs related to transportation and handling costs.

Table 1. The Cost Performance % of Distribution Cost reduction Related to (Transportation and Handling Costs)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Low	7	28.0	28.0	28.0
	Low	8	32.0	32.0	60.0
	Medium	10	40.0	40.0	100.0
	Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Manufacturing Cost (Labor and Maintenance)

The table shows that 08 firms out of 25 firms have a very low deficient % reduction of manufacturing cost, 10 out of 25 firms have a

low % reduction of manufacturing cost, and 7 out of 25 firms have a medium % reduction of manufacturing cost. Therefore, the maximum number of 10 pulses are low percentage of manufacturing cost.

Table 2. The % of Reduction of Manufacturing Cost (Labor and Maintenance) of All Pulse Firms

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Low	8	32.0	32.0	32.0
	Low	10	40.0	40.0	72.0
	Medium	7	28.0	28.0	100.0
	Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Inventory Cost

The table shows that 09 firms, out of 25 firms, are very low % reduction in total inventory cost, 11 firms are low % reduction in total inventory

cost, and five firms had a medium % reduction in total inventory cost. Therefore, the large number of 11 pulses firms has a low percentage of inventory cost.

Table 3. The % Reduction of Total Inventory Cost of All Pulse's Firms

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Low	9	36.0	36.0	36.0
	Low	11	44.0	44.0	80.0
	Medium	5	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Warehouse Cost

The table shows that 10 pulses firms are very low % reduction of warehouse cost, 12 had a low % reduction of warehouse cost, and 3 pulses firms

had a medium % reduction of warehouse cost. Therefore, the large number of 12 pulse firms are low percentage of the warehouse cost of all pulse firms.

Table 4. The % of Reduction of Warehouse Cost (Year-over-Year) of All Pulse Firms

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Low	10	40.0	40.0	40.0
	Low	12	48.0	48.0	88.0
	Medium	3	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Supply Chain Cost

The table shows that seven firms had a deficient, very low % reduction of total supply chain cost (year-over-year)), and 10 out of 25 firms had a

low % reduction of supply chain cost. Eight firms showed a medium % reduction in complete supply chain cost. Therefore, the large number of pulse firms size 10 has a low percentage of supply chain cost.

Table 5. The Reduction of Total Supply Chain Cost

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Low	7	28.0	28.0	28.0
	Low	10	40.0	40.0	68.0
	Medium	8	32.0	32.0	100.0
	Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Return on Investment

The table shows that six pulses firms generate low returns on investment, the other nine firms generate medium returns on investment, and a

high number of ten firms have a high rate of return on investment. Therefore, the large maximum number (10) pulses firms generates a high rate of return on investment for all pulse firms.

Table 6. The Table Shows the Return on Investment of All Pulse Firms

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Low	6	24.0	24.0	24.0
	Medium	9	36.0	36.0	60.0
	High	10	40.0	40.0	100.0
	Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation

The table includes the ANOVA technique and balanced scorecard method, which measure the sustainability performance of all pulses firms and their pulses value chain. The tables generate

different values related to the sum of the square and frequency and generate the significance level of risk of all sustainability factors. The table performed the comparison of all factors with the standard level of significance (.05).

Table 7. ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Delivery	Between Groups	.881	2	.440	1.722	.202
	Within Groups	5.626	22	.256		
	Total	6.507	24			
Responsiveness	Between Groups	.796	2	.398	2.878	.078
	Within Groups	3.044	22	.138		
	Total	3.840	24			
Cost	Between Groups	.065	2	.032	.264	.770
	Within Groups	2.695	22	.123		
	Total	2.760	24			
Resource	Between Groups	.071	2	.035	.084	.920
	Within Groups	9.245	22	.420		
	Total	9.316	24			
Flexibility	Between Groups	.063	2	.031	.121	.887
	Within Groups	5.727	22	.260		
	Total	5.790	24			
Quality	Between Groups	.380	2	.190	.878	.430
	Within Groups	4.765	22	.217		
	Total	5.146	24			
Innovative	Between Groups	.507	2	.253	.793	.465
	Within Groups	7.033	22	.320		
	Total	7.540	24			

The Table ANOVA techniques determine the values of different levels of significance of risk factors that does not impact the performance of pulses firms, from the following table 2.1 all the value of levels of significance does not impact the performance of pulses firms that show the maximum number of pulses firms does not adopt the sustainability factors and balanced score card entities.

The following table determines the different values generated through the analysis of data. The delivery factors that generate the frequency value 1.722. and the level of significance of factors is .202 as compared to the standard significance value of 0.05, which shows that the delivery factor does not impact the performance of all pulse firms. The responsive factors are another PMMS factor to generates a frequency value of 2.878 and the level of significance of

factors is 0.78, as compared to the standard level of significance level.05, shows that the responsive factors does not impact the sustainability performance of all pulses firms and their value chain practices. The cost factors are another generate the frequency value of .264 and their level of significance of factors at .770, which shows the cost factors may not impact the sustainability performance of all pulse's firms. The resource factors generate the frequency value at 0.084, also generate the level of significance of factors are 0.920, as compared to the standard level of significance is 0.05 that the resources factor does not impact the performance of pulses firms. Similarly, the flexibility factors generate the frequency F value at .121, and their level of significance of factors are .887, as compared to the standard level of significance are 0.05 which shows that flexibility

factors does not impact the sustainability performance of the pulses value chain of all pulses firms. The other sustainability factor is quality, which generates a frequency value of .878, also the level of significance of factors is 0.430, as compared to the standard level of significance are 0.05, which shows the quality factors does not impact the sustainability performance of the pulses value chain. The other sustainability factors of innovative factors generate a frequency value of .793, and their level of significance is .465, which implies the innovation techniques does not impact the sustainability performance of all pulses firms and their pulses value chain practices.

Conclusion

The result generates Information through a balanced scorecard method to evaluate the firms' performance. The expected outcomes show that high-level firms do not implement sustainability measures and balance scorecard methods for the enhancement of company performance. The study briefly defined the balanced card method and its framework structure, which consists of different levels implemented according to the hierarchy level of firms and every level has its function and different sustainability measure factors to improve the internal and external parts of firms. The balanced scorecard promotes sustainability measures based on their four dimensions financial, customer, internal process, learning, and growth perspectives, and controls the usage of all natural resources. The study determines the level of significance values that show different sustainability factors do not have an impact on the performance of pulses firms. Therefore a large number of pulses firms are facing constraints related to machine breakdown, lack of resources, lack of availability of quality seeds, poor response time, less return on investment, etc. are the major issues, that pulses firms are facing, the government must take initiative to upgrade the processing process provide the facilities so that pulses firms implement the pulse value chain practices to provide value-added product and service and enhance the supply chain management of pulses

firms. Both methods help to investigate the actual status of selected pulse firms and define the urgent requirement to adopt the sustainability measure, performance measure, and management system approach to evaluate the pulse firms in their production and operational part. Similarly, balanced scorecard practices help to achieve financial gain, generate bonding with the customer, and develop internal processes, also promote learning and growth, and opportunity for pulses firms. The selected pulse firms are immediately to adopt the balanced scored techniques to improve their supply chain management as well as provide value-added products and services through the concept of pulse value chain. All twenty-five pulse processing firms of selected regions of India were required to achieve the expected performance of pulses firms and performed evaluation based on 24 financial and nonfinancial indicators of sustainability measurement tool, which has based upon the dimension of the balanced scorecard and PMMS. It helps to improve communication and develop understanding among employees in firms and provides relevant information that is applied for strategic decision making generates a competitive environment also places the product in a better environment.

Recommendation

- a. All pulses processing firms are required to adopt sustainability practices and effective supply chain management which reduces the risk of machine breakdown, old inventory, and breakage in supply chain management. and allowed the government should interfere in supporting all pulse firms by generating policy-making, long-term plans reducing taxes, and providing subsidies for new machine technology, and farming practices.
- b. The government should participate and play an active role in providing training and development regarding pulse value chain practices to all firm owners, farmers, and intermedia, also generate awareness and provide the potential benefit of the pulses value chain and other farming practices.

c. Every pulses firms are required to adopt the sustainability dimension in their manufacturing process and operate green supply chain management, to reduce the toxic gas and emission and provide a green and pollution-free environment.

d. The government should make agencies to provide the facilities of quality seeds, and fertilizer and fulfill the requirement to establish the pulse value chain practices in all pulse firms. Also provides the warehouse and logistic management facility as well as enhanced the supply chain management of every firms.

Limitation

The limitation of the study are the pulse firms are selected from three states has based upon turnover, size, and production capacity. The case study adopted quantitative techniques (PMMS) and the balance card method to measure the sustainability performance of pulses firms and generate sustainability measure to generate efficient pulses firms practices. The performance measurement and management system provides in-depth Information regarding measurement techniques of all factors. It shows all pulses firms facing constraints and have not adopted any sustainability measures through interpretation the generated value determines the pulses firms are facing constraints in different parts of pulses firms. The research study adopted only the balanced scored cards and PMMS performance measurement and management system quantitative techniques which analyse the internal and external factors of pulses firms and provide relevant information related to all factors. The study covered only the pulses firms, which briefly defined the importance of sustainability measures in the pulses firms.

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